

Only the Most Important Thing

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In one word, the most glaring “misconception” about Israel-Palestine is “context”—literally the fountain from which all else flows, including an array of misplaced assumptions, arbitrary historical starting points, misnomers, and, most significantly, glaring blind spots.

These shortcomings are not solely a matter of lack of knowledge or information, but a matter of interpretive lenses. We may all be looking at the same thing(s), especially in the past 6 months of a slaughter, yet not all understand it as the same thing. For millions, including the 17 members of the International Court of Justice, it is a plausible genocide. Yet, for many others, it is the gruesome and necessary cost of war.

Perhaps the first order of misconceptions is the misnomer “conflict” in Israel-Palestine—though its usage depends on intention. A conflict in regional and international relations usually exists between two parties who are equal in relation to their status, notably of sovereignty. In the case of Israel-Palestine, we have a relationship of subjugation: one sovereign party (Israel) and another non-sovereign party (Palestinians) that is completely dependent on the former, not least by virtue of the effective military occupation under which it survives. Under these conditions, the ensuing

relationship is not one of contention between two equal parties fighting over land, resources, or anything else. It is a relation of subjugation, by brute and vastly disproportionate force, of one party by another, daily, consistently, unwaveringly, and almost completely, for many decades. Enter context. Any immediate encounter with such subjugation involves witnessing a *military occupation* as an essential starting point: Walls, checkpoints, restricted movement, home demolitions, random and frequent raids, land and other property confiscation, arbitrary detention and imprisonment, total administrative control of people and goods entering and leaving the territory via land, sea, and air, total control of basic resources (food, water, energy sources)—all occurring with impunity. Since the Second Intifada in 2000, military occupation has also been compounded by warfare, or the use of military force against Palestinians living under occupation (i.e., siege, extrajudicial assassinations, shoot to kill, aerial missile strikes).

Beyond framing, we witness the building of new realities on the ground via long-term forms of dispossession whereby land/villages/towns inhabited by one people (Palestinians) are systematically replaced with permanent settlements for another people (Israelis). This occurred within, as well as outside, the

borders delineated by the United Nations Partition Plan of 1947. There is a term for this systematic process: *settler colonialism*.

In turn, we witness the existence of two legal frameworks that govern two sets of people based on their racial/ethnic background: one for Jewish-Israelis and another for Palestinians. Within the context of both military occupation on the one hand, and a systematic and unabated process of ethnic cleansing on the other, this legal distinction and duality becomes possible and increasingly concrete. There is a term for this systemic form of discrimination: *apartheid*.

While these realities—military occupation, settler colonialism, and Apartheid—have evoked objections and shock among supporters of the state of Israel historically, the unanimous convergence of nearly all independent human rights and legal organizations on all three dimensions of the Israel-Palestine context addressed above has been resounding in recent years. Yet, the “shock” and consternation in some circles at the mention of these terms at every historical juncture during the past few decades reminds us that the elision of context and history might well make people, including political scientists of the first order, believe that we are witnessing a conflict between two parties. We have now come full circle.

Plainly and simply, what political science can do to is to reintroduce the context of subjugation. This is buttressed by the brutally glaring power differential between the two parties in question— in terms of military, financial, administrative, and relational power at the level of external patronage, provided by the most powerful country in human history, the United States. Incorporating such vast relational and power differentials into the

analysis transforms existing discussions on the matter from cultural to political ones that are subject to the falsifiable frameworks and methods applied in the better corners of the field. ♦